

Mini-review

Decision-making for timely euthanasia in “end-of-career” dairy cows

Clémence Lesimple, Isabelle Veissier

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Decision-making for timely euthanasia in “end-of-career” dairy cows

Clémence Lesimple^{1,2}, Isabelle Veissier²

¹ESA, Angers 49000, France

²Université Clermont Auvergne, INRAE, VetAgro Sup, UMR Herbivores, Saint-Genès-Champanelle, 63122, France

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1. The issue

The management of dairy cows at the end of their career raises important ethical issues, particularly when the animals are removed from the milking herd because of compromised health. Euthanasia is an important tool to humanely end an animal’s life when there is an irremediable welfare compromise, such as disease or pain and suffering that cannot be cured or alleviated (Reid et al., 2018). The management of end-of-career dairy cows also raises the issue of animal fitness for transport because an animal unfit for transport cannot be taken to the slaughterhouse, even if its condition does not pose a risk to food safety.

The decision to euthanise an animal is a multi-step process that must fit an appropriate agenda to prevent both unnecessary suffering and overuse of euthanasia (Reid et al., 2018; Walker et al., 2020), and to facilitate action for the person responsible (Rollin, 1986). Euthanasia also means a loss of economic value for the farmers, because the animal cannot be sold for consumption, and incurs costs with necessary fees for both the euthanasia itself (veterinary intervention / purchase of materials and products) and the removal and destruction of the carcass (Dolecheck, 2018). These economic considerations can hinder the decision-making.

The present review focuses on the literature on timely euthanasia in dairy cows.

2. Summary of the scientific knowledge¹

2.1. Access to information

Despite its crucial importance, little is known about the euthanasia rate on dairy farms. Most scientific studies deal with the mortality rate in general, including euthanasia and unassisted death (Garry & McConnel, 2012; McFarlane et al., 2022; Toaff-Rosenstein, 2018). Mortality rates in Canada and the USA have been estimated at 2-6% and 1-5% per year respectively (Thomsen & Houe, 2006). Mortality has increased steadily over the last two decades (Compton et al., 2017).

Reliable information on euthanasia decision-making is difficult to obtain, as farmers are reluctant to answer questions specifically related to mortality (Canada: 54% of the respondents in Roche et al., 2019, up to 71% in Winder et al., 2018). Reports of low euthanasia rates (USA: only 9/34 dairy farms reported euthanasia in the last three years in Husfeldt & Endres, 2012; Canada: 33% of the farmers in Winder et al., 2018) could be a result of farmers being unwilling to report. Alternatively, it could be a result of injured or sick cattle (including cows affected by Downer Cow Syndrome, **DCS**) not being

¹ The scientific reviews prepared for CARE4DAIRY focused on the literature of the last 10 years, assuming that older articles have already been taken into account in current technical recommendations. Older articles may be cited if they provide complementary knowledge.

euthanised but left to die, leading to serious welfare problems (Husfeldt & Endres, 2012; Toaff-Rosenstein, 2018). The ability to carry out on-farm emergency slaughter varies considerably between countries, even within the EU, and may directly influence the prevalence of euthanasia (McDermott et al., 2023; Skuladottir et al., 2022).

2.2. Reasons for and timing of euthanasia

Mobility disorders appear the primary reasons for euthanasia: lameness (with or without mention of severity, Denmark: Dolecheck, 2018; USA: Wagner et al., 2020b), traumatic injuries (USA: Wagner et al., 2020a, 2020b), non-ambulatory cattle regardless of the reason for loss of mobility (USA: Cramer et al., 2019). Non-ambulatory cattle are sometimes transported to save the economic value of the animal although this is illegal (Endres & Schwartzkopf-Genswein, 2018).

Most national and international programmes or regulations agree on the situations in which euthanasia should be mandatory (Braun et al., 2019; Cockram, 2021; Kasperbauer & Sandøe, 2015; Khol et al., 2016; Shearer, 2013, 2018; Walker et al., 2020). These situations are summarised in Table 1 below, along with requirements for farmers to have the knowledge and skills to identify them.

Table 1. Animal conditions requiring euthanasia and the farmer’s skills required to identify them

Condition of the animal	Requirement for the farmer
Animal in severe pain, distress or suffering that cannot be relieved,	Recognition of signals indicating pain and suffering
Animal not responding to treatment or requiring prolonged antibiotic treatment	Work in contact with the vet, at least basic knowledge of common injuries and diseases and their possible treatments
Animal chronically ill	
Animal unfit for transport and not meeting on-farm slaughter criteria	Evaluation and recognition of the severity of the condition
Animal that cannot be saved	

In case of DCS, it is generally accepted that euthanasia should be performed after 24 h, because the chances of recovery are very low due to the likelihood of secondary lesions (Canada: Puerto-Parada et al., 2021; McFarlane et al., 2022 for review). In addition, dairy cows with abomasal ulcers are often euthanised after 24-48 h of unsuccessful treatment (Braun et al. 2019). However, in most cases, there is no clear cut-off point in the animal’s condition to decide on euthanasia (Walker et al., 2020). The assessment of the situation is left to the individual caring for the animal (Endres & Schwartzkopf-Genswein, 2018), if veterinary advice is not sought. The welfare of the animal is often not the only aspect considered by farmers when deciding to euthanise. The owner’s attachment to the animal

and economic and production factors also play a role (Cockram, 2021; Khol et al., 2016; Littlewood et al., 2021).

2.3. Person in charge

The use of euthanasia can be a psychological and even moral burden (Edwards-Callaway et al., 2022; Edwards-Callaway, 2018; Román-Muñiz et al., 2021). Farmers may be reluctant to perform the act, especially if they are caring for the animals themselves, and as a result they may unintentionally prolong the animals’ suffering (Endres & Schwartzkopf-Genswein, 2018; Wagner et al., 2020a). Farmers and animal caretakers should therefore be trained to recognise situations in which an animal’s welfare is severely compromised (Cockram, 2021; Husfeldt & Endres, 2012; Koralesky & Fraser, 2019; Merenda et al., 2022; Román-Muñiz et al., 2021; Toaff-Rosenstein, 2018; Walker et al., 2020). In other cases, it may be the emotional and moral burden of seeing an animal suffering and being unable to provide effective treatment that is the main driver of the farmer’s decision to euthanise. When made by farm workers, the decision to euthanise depends more on the person’s compassion for the animal and on their perception of the situation than on clinical signs (Edwards-Callaway et al., 2022; Merenda et al., 2022).

In cases where farmers rely on the veterinarian’s decision to euthanise an animal, there may be an increased waiting time depending on the availability of vets. However, the presence of a veterinarian ensures the respect for animal welfare as veterinarians are expected to be trained to recognise signs of pain and suffering and to euthanise using appropriate methods.

2.4. Consequences of untimely euthanasia

If the decision to euthanise is not made in time, the welfare of the animal is likely to be severely compromised. In the US, Brazil and Europe, nearly 4% of dairy cattle arrive at slaughter with severe welfare problems (Vogel et al., 2019); The majority of these animals were probably unfitted for transport and should have been euthanised or slaughtered on farm. Alternatively, end-of-career cows that are unfit for transport may die unassisted on the farm (Toaff-Rosenstein, 2018). A high ratio of unassisted deaths to euthanasia is a clear warning sign of poor animal welfare.

3. Recommendations

To avoid prolonged animal suffering:

- Animals at high risk of suffering should be euthanised or slaughtered on-farm for private consumption before they suffer intensely and become unfit for human consumption. Such a decision is to be based on a health and welfare prognosis.
- Farmers / animal caretakers should be trained to recognise situations where the welfare of an animal is seriously compromised.
- Farmers / animal caretakers should be trained to assess fitness for transport. An animal should not be transported if it is moderately or severely lame, close to parturition (>90% gestation), febrile, has wounds of at least moderate-severe wounds, recumbent or even moribund. It is the responsibility of the haulier not to accept such animals on a vehicle.
- Guidelines and decision-making processes to be applied when an animal is suffering should be made explicit in a standard operating procedure (Cockram, 2021; Endres & Schwartzkopf-Genswein, 2018; Fogsgaarg et al., 2016; Koralesky & Fraser, 2018, 2019; Merenda et al., 2022; Román-Muñoz et al., 2021; Walker et al., 2020). Such a procedure can be established together with the veterinarian. Below we propose a decision tree that can be adapted to fit farmers’ motivations, values and potential economic considerations (Figure 1). To develop a standard operating procedure, the decision tree should be supplemented with animal signs to identify suffering states and fitness for transport.
- The support of an external person (especially the veterinarian) helps to ensure the timeliness of the decision (of treatment, slaughter or euthanasia) while reducing the emotional and moral burden on the farmer (Edwards-Callaway et al., 2022; Littlewood et al., 2021; Merenda et al., 2022; Wagner et al., 2020b).
- Euthanasia and unassisted death should be reported separately in farm records.
- In some countries, farmers are allowed to slaughter (for household consumption) or euthanise cattle themselves (e.g. Switzerland and Sweden). This is likely to reduce the risk of animals being left to die unassisted. However, this is not permitted in all countries. Discussions on euthanasia / slaughter by farmers should take place at national / European level.

In case of sickness / injury

Figure 1. Decision tree for euthanasia decision making

Further studies should be carried out to

- Identify clear behavioural and health signs to aid euthanasia decision-making (see also the Care4Dairy minireview on recognition of pain signs: de Boyer Des Roches et al., 2024)
- Identify the reasons for unassisted dying, the barriers that prevent farmers from carrying out euthanasia and the barriers that prevent them from reporting euthanasia
- Investigate methods that farmers could use to slaughter cattle on-farm

Other animals from dairy herds

Timely euthanasia in dairy herds does not only concern end-of-career cows. The careers of heifers and calves may also be terminated early for health or other reasons. There is a lack of scientific literature on the reasons for terminating the lives of heifers and calves and the conditions under which it is done. A bibliographic search in Web of Science (« dairy calf » AND « euthanasia ») yielded 42 articles, of which 6 did not distinguish between euthanasia and unassisted death, 2 were on euthanasia of adult cattle (included in the present document), and the remaining 34 were on experimental calves euthanised at the end of an experiment. Male dairy calves have a low economic value, and very young (unweaned) calves are usually not accepted by slaughterhouses. The mortality of male dairy calves is higher than that of female dairy calves and higher than that of beef calves (Reismus et al 2017; Boyle and Mee, 2021). There is reason to believe that some male dairy calves are killed on the farm or left to die unattended.

The general principles described in this review can be adapted for heifers and calves.

4. Literature search

Search equations in Web of Sciences:

- 1- (dairy cattle) AND (euthanasia), Jan 2012-June 2022
- 2- (dairy cattle) AND (on-farm euthanasia), Jan 2012-June 2022

All the papers of the second search were included in the first one.

Number of results: 73

Selection process: 14 publications kept amongst which 3 are congress summaries without associated article.

No. publications excluded	Reasons for exclusion
10	Not on the right species
8	Risk factors for mortality rate
35	Euthanasia mentioned as a consequence of a condition (mostly disease) without details
4	Case study for 1 disease
1	Study on euthanized animals
1	Not on farm

Search equation in Google Scholar:

- 1- “euthanasia” AND “dairy cattle” → 2440 results.
- 2- “euthanasia” AND “dairy cattle” AND “decision making” → 404 results

Only the papers with the keywords in the title or abstract were extracted: 54 results

Selection process: 18 publications kept.

No. publications excluded	Reasons for exclusion
9	Not possible to identify euthanasia and unassisted death
6	Methods for euthanise, not decision making
1	Not on the right species
20	Euthanasia mentioned as a consequence of a condition (mostly disease) without details

Additional research

1- In WoS: (Involuntary cull) AND (Dairy cattle), Jan 2012-June 2022

Number of results: 36

Selection process: 0 publications kept. The term involuntary culling intrinsically gathers euthanasia and unassisted death. It was thus not possible to identify the reasons leading to euthanasia.

No. publications excluded	Reasons for exclusion
23	Not possible to identify euthanasia and unassisted death
13	Euthanasia only mentioned as a consequence of a condition

2- In Google Scholar: (Involuntary cull) AND (Dairy cattle), 2012- 2022

Number of results: 25

Selection process: 0 publications kept. Same reason as above.

No. publications excluded	Reasons for exclusion
8	Not possible to identify euthanasia and unassisted death
15	Involuntary culling only mentioned as a consequence of a condition
2	Already in the WoS search

Total number of papers: 32 + 4 added manually

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